

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING DIGITAL STORYTELLING TECHNIQUE IN MULTICULTURAL CLASSROOMS IN ORDER TO RAISE AWARENESS OF TRANSNATIONALISM

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ABSTRACT

English classrooms became more colorful, interactive recent years. Teachers need to work a lot developing their teaching skills and methods as young generation of today's technologically developed century demand high quality education. Teacher should be capable of recognizing different socio-cultural problems apart from educational in the second language and foreign language acquisition classroom. In this case introducing outstanding, enjoyable and at the same to effective teaching techniques are considered as a valuable, significant tool to conduct lessons. Especially multicultural classes need this kind of interactive, technology based activities in order to shape social, cultural communication. In this process assessment part also plays crucial role as learners will improve their skills more during independent, self-study time. Tasks which are given by teacher should be relevant to topic and should serve learners to develop skills working in groups in order to form awareness of transnationalism in the SLA and FLA classroom. According to Brown (2010) in order to achieve expected results during the teaching process the assessment tool should include some principles like practicality, validity, reliability, authenticity and washback. Digital storytelling can justify all this criteria and this article contains evidence to this view.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, technology creates myriad of opportunities for people in different fields. Especially, it is being used in education widely to improve the productiveness of the lesson as Oxford stated (1990, p. 8) using various strategies make learning process easier, more enjoyable, faster and more effective.. Technology contributed to migrant learners also in this case. This article is

about the usage of technology in migrant learners' life which enables them to obtain their voice in target society. Day by day the number of people who are applying to foreign universities is increasing. Mobile communication, social media they easily can keep in touch with their countries and shape transnationalism. Transnational literacy is the way of providing variety cultural awareness, particular knowledge which aids learners to understand better their linguistics and culture which differs

from others. They are no longer accepted just as migrants. They are considered as transnationalists who have a strong contact with their home country and trying to build relations with the host country. It may be difficult for migrant learners to adopt new cultural and social norms. They may feel themselves inconvenient towards native peers whose speaking is fluent. Teachers need to improve literacies taking into consideration learners' degrees of affiliation, material condition and how their thinking ability developed.

Transnational literacy means being literate in different other cultures where learners value, appreciate their peer's cultural beliefs, norms, worldview. The usage of technology aids to develop transnational identities. This awareness serves migrant learners to shape their right to speak in particular context. Migrant learners often face with inequality because of racial views of elite groups. Racism makes migrants feel isolated and undervalued. This really influences their learning process. In this case teachers should be instructors who create friendly atmosphere, construct environment where multicultural students' beliefs valued. Jimenez, Smith & Tengue (as cited in Darvin & Norton 2014) mentioned that transnational literacies serve learners to comprehend the better understanding of multicultural beliefs and their linguistics. Creating identity texts enable students to respect not only each other's linguistic identities but also metalinguistic skills.

Digital stories are the best way to overcome the issues of migrant learners. It is becoming the innovative way of creating personal stories. Digital stories are brief personal stories which are done through

technology using images, words. Students need to use different images, sound effects, voices using technology. Moreover, learners can use their mother tongue but with English subtitles. Incorporating technology into classroom really makes lesson effective and beneficial for learners as it brings into classroom authenticity. Learners in multicultural classes may be aware of personal stories of their peers who come from different countries which increase empathy and begin to appreciate different cultures. Since, there are some L2 learners who reject to accept target cultural norms. As Ishihara and Cohen (2010) stated learners with resistance to use L2 pragmatic norms obtain strong beliefs toward their own cultural norms. However, this greatly impact to learning process. In this case digital storytelling highly contributes to involve into target context and create The Third Space where migrant learners accept L2 pragmatic norms saving their own cultural norms. They accommodate into target context.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

In the project in Vancouver which is considered multicultural city the process of making digital stories consists of 4 phases. This program was held on in secondary school covering 3 months.

The first phase is **story construction** where pupils learn different genres reading stories. In this phase learners need to make their own stories. They were asked to create story relying on their personal experience including pieces from their culture, traditions, religion.

The second one is called **multimodal selection** which enables students to use appropriate images, sounds according to

the meaning. After making ready their stories they were instructed to choose various images and sounds related to their story. In this phase learners need creativity in order to find relative images.

In the third phase which is known as **storyboard design**, learners practice how to construct concise, coherent stories. This part was the most interesting as learners enjoyed making their stories with the help of chosen images and sounds. It demanded learners to think logically and critically as they should consider the sequence of images while working on this project. Designing stories in laptops made the process even more enjoyable.

The last process is **editing** where students are provided with digital skills so as to create videos. The most crucial part made learners to work hard. Before starting instructors taught them how to edit videos, include sounds and music.

Teachers' role in this process is guiding, instructing students and providing them with necessary information while workshops give them an opportunity to exchange ideas, get peer feedback. The usage of personal stories with the help of videos improves transnational literacy which enables learners to be aware of each others' cultural beliefs, social norms. They begin to respect cultures which are different from their own creating relationships between each other.

When project was ended interview was taken from participants in order to identify effectiveness rate of digital storytelling. It helped so much to realize privileges and downsides of this project work which serves to facilitate the teaching technique.

RESULTS

Secondary school learners were chosen for this project as at this age learners take high interest on technology, interactive methods. Learners were enthusiastic during these 3 months from the beginning to the end. It helped them to improve not only fluency, accuracy in English language acquisition but also transnational literacy.

In the first phase learners had not any difficulty. Since, they created stories based on their personal life. They tried to show their colorful traditions and customs while making stories. Teachers observed the classroom and helped learners who could not start their stories or logically connect ideas. When they finished their stories they were asked to check and correct if there are any mistakes.

They started second phase with great enthusiasm as they can use any images even photos of their childhood for their stories. Besides they should include different sounds like knocking, walking, sound of the rain, wind or voices of people, animal which made the process energetic. Learners were very creative and used several tools for making their story appealing and outstanding.

Storyboard design part urged learners to think a lot. Some learners faced difficulties in this part. They were asked to form story with logically connected images which are appropriate. In this process they had to miss some images or search another appropriate one. It demanded critical and logical thinking which can be complicated for secondary class learners.

The last and the most difficult but at the same time the most intriguing part was editing. Finally, they could create their story on laptop using digital skills. Including animations, gifs, images and voices to their digital stories was really enjoyable and fun. However, it was visible that some learners from remote places struggled in using digital technology. They got helpful instructions from teachers and managed to tackle this issue.

Interview which was taken after project clarified that this technique can be really fruitful in multicultural classes. All learners from different countries realized that people have their own identities, personality traits according to their nationality, religion, culture, tradition and social norms. Their view towards project was positive and they wanted to continue this project in their classrooms.

DISCUSSION

According to gained results the view of effectiveness digital stories in transnational classes was proved. Learners and teachers immediately after project could see the progress. Even learners who have no any interest to lessons, learning English language started to show interest. It improved integrative motivation of learners in the classroom. What's more, Wong and Nunan (2011) stated that authentic use also may contribute to successful language learning. They stated that more successful learners utilize authentic conversations by communicating with their peers by sharing personal stories and enlarging vocabulary with help of authentic materials such as videos, images. Contrary to this, less successful learners rely on their teacher and prefer

more reading materials. Therefore, communicative competence which main focus of this project contributed to improve fluency, accuracy, vocabulary and high confidence of making speech in front of audience.

Cohen and Olshtain (as cited in Ishihara & Cohen 2010) mentioned that in order to obtain native-like manner in second language pragmatics learners need to live at least ten years in that context. So, at the early period of coming to another country can be really challenging for migrant learners. It creates such new environment where learners undergo different adaptation stages. It takes time to adjust environment, to be accustomed to the cultural norms of target language. Implementing technology to this process helps to obtain more productive lesson and achieve higher results.

This project helped them to see these differences and accept it. This article closely connected with article "Motivation, leadership and organization: Do American theories apply to abroad" by Hofstede. He presented the particular cultural norms of American people. According Hofstede (1980) culture is mental programming which forms in the certain environment. It is not characteristic of individuals, It includes group of peoples who receive the same educational system and social life experience. So, it is essential consider these factors while teaching multicultural classes. There may be especially, problems with power distance as Hofstede (1980) pointed out that power distance is status of communities and identifying the difference between large and small power distance communities. Unfortunately, some migrant learners come across with this inequality

in the classroom. Improving transnational literacy using digital stories help multicultural learners become close and understand, support each other as working collaboratively is much more effective in acquisition process.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion in this modern developed society there are myriad of factors which teacher needs to take into account. Digital storytelling can be useful not only to improve language skills but it highly motivates learners and attracts them to the lessons. Teacher easily can involve students into this activity. Creating stories, clips in different topics can be beneficial to

improve students' transnational literacy. Visual aids always considered as a special tool which make lesson more memorable and interactive. Moreover, learners can develop their digital literacy which is essential in today's life.

Communicative competence which became essential also can be practiced efficiently through this activity. The importance of using digital stories is that where learners learn digital skills, improve language skills and raise awareness of transnational literacy. It helps them to create strong relationship among their peers which is significant in the classroom.

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